

Heterocyclic Quinones. Part II : Synthesis of Benzo-(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(h,h') Pyrrocoline Quinones

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A series of unsymmetrical disubstituted benzo-(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(h, h') pyrrocoline quinones have been synthesised by condensing chloranil with active methylene compounds and quinoline which gave only the *trans* form of the compound as shown by colour reaction and TLC. The deep colour of these compounds is attributed to the betaine structure as one of the contributing form.

IN a previous communication¹ we have described the synthesis of benzo-(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(f,f') pyrrocoline quinones. This reaction has been extended to the synthesis of benzo-(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(h,h') pyrrocoline quinones by the reaction of chloranil with active methylene compounds and quinoline. The structure of these compounds has been established by affording evidence based on colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid², which have also been used to distinguish them from one another.

Interaction of chloranil with reactive methylene compounds and quinoline gave the respective 7:15-disubstituted benzo-(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(h,h') pyrrocoline quinones (I). All these compounds did not melt upto 356° and gave blue to violet colour in concentrated sulphuric acid, which turned into red colour on basification followed by precipitation. The blue colour reappeared on addition of concentrated sulphuric acid. The colour reactions of these compounds indicate that the products should have *trans* configuration, which is the only product

isolated in this case. The formation of *cis* structure in this case also, seems to be sterically hindered.

Experimental Procedure

All melting points have been determined on a Kofler instrument and are uncorrected. General procedure adopted for the preparation of the benzo-(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(h,h')-pyrrocoline quinones is as given below.

A mixture of chloranil (1 mole), reactive methylene compound (1 mole) and quinoline (1 mole) in 25-30 ml. absolute alcohol was heated under reflux on a water bath for 4 hours., when all the chloranil dissolved and a deeply coloured reaction mixture was obtained. The product separated on cooling was filtered and washed with ethanol, ether, hot water and then dried. The product was recrystallised from the desired solvent.

TABLE—1 7:15 DISUBSTITUTED-BENZO (1:2-b, 4:5-b') DIBENZ(H,H') PYRROCOLINE QUINONES(I)

S. No.	Active methylene compound used	Molecular formula	Crystallised form	Colour	M.P. °C	Elemental analysis			Elemental analysis Required		
						C%	Found H%	N%	C%	H%	N%
1.	Ethyl acetoacetate	C ₃₂ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₆	Pyridine	Red	does not melt upto 356°	72.3	3.9	5.2	72.4	4.1	5.2
2.	Malonic ester	C ₃₂ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₆	Pyridine	Brown red	does not melt upto 356°	72.4	4.0	5.1	72.4	4.1	5.2
3.	Acetyl acetone	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	Pyridine	Brown	does not melt upto 356°	76.5	3.8	5.9	76.5	3.8	5.9
4.	Benzoyl acetone	C ₄₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	Pyridine	Dark red	does not melt upto 356°	80.6	3.5	4.5	80.8	3.6	4.6
5.	Methyl cyanide	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂	Benzene + dioxane	Green	does not melt upto 356°	77.2	2.6	12.8	77.3	2.7	12.8

Mechanism :

The following reaction mechanism for the formation of 7:15 disubstituted-benzo(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(h, h') pyrrocoline quinones has been given

where

1. $R_1 = -COOCH_2 \cdot CH_3$
2. $R_1 = -COOCH_2 \cdot C \cdot H_3$
3. $R_1 = -COCH_3$
4. $R_1 = -COC_6H_5$
5. $R_1 = -CN$

and it conforms the fact that it is the more electron attracting group R which is cleaved during the course of reaction as supported by experimental evidence.

The dyeing characteristics of these compounds is under investigation.

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References

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